

1 **An HD-ZIP-MYB complex regulates glandular secretory trichome initiation in**
2 ***Artemisia annua* L.**

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16 **Running title:** HD-ZIP IV- MYB complexes regulate GST initiation.

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26 **Summary**

- 27 ● Plant glandular secretory trichomes (GSTs) produce various specialized
28 metabolites. Increasing GST density represents a strategy to enhance the yield of
29 these chemicals; however, the gene regulatory network that controls GST initiation
30 remains unclear.
- 31 ● In a previous study of *Artemisia annua* L., we found that a HD-ZIP IV transcription
32 factor, AaHD1, promotes GST initiation by directly regulating *AaGSW2*. Here, we
33 identified two AaHD1-interacting MIXTA/MIXTA-like transcription factors,
34 named AaMYB16 and AaMYB5.
- 35 ● Through the generation and characterization of transgenic plants, we found that
36 AaMYB16 is a positive regulator of GST initiation, while AaMYB5 has the
37 opposite effect. Notably, neither of them regulates GST formation independently.
38 Rather, they act competitively, by interacting and modulating AaHD1 promoter
39 binding activity. Additionally, the phytohormone jasmonic acid (JA) was shown to
40 be associated with the AaHD1-AaMYB16/AaMYB5 regulatory network through
41 transcriptional regulation via a JASMONATE-ZIM DOMAIN (JAZ) protein
42 repressor.
- 43 ● These results bring new insight into the mechanism of GST initiation through
44 regulatory complexes, which appear to have similar functions in a range of vascular
45 plant taxa.

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47 **Key words:** Glandular secretory trichome; HD-ZIP; MYB; complex; regulator;
48 jasmonic acid; *Artemisia annua*

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51 **Introduction**

52 Trichomes are hair-like epidermal structures that are present on aerial parts of most
53 plant species (Payne, 1978). They are generally classified as glandular or non-glandular
54 (Johnson, 1975; Mathur & Chua, 2000). Glandular secretory trichomes (GSTs), which
55 are found in about 30% of all vascular plants, are multicellular and are commonly
56 comprised of three parts: a base, a stalk, and a gland (Fahn, 2000). The latter gives GSTs
57 the capacity to store and secrete specialized metabolites (Liu *et al.*, 2019), many of
58 which are used commercially as natural pesticides, food additives, fragrance ingredients,
59 or pharmaceuticals (Schuurink & Tissier, 2019). Examples include essential oil extracts
60 from GSTs of the Lamiaceae family, such as mint (*Mentha spicata*), basil (*Ocimum*
61 *basilicum*), lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*), oregano (*Origanum vulgare*), and thyme
62 (*Thymus vulgaris*) (Bini & Giuliani, 2006). Another notable example is the anti-malaria
63 drug artemisinin, which is produced in the GSTs of *Artemisia annua* L. (Graham *et al.*,
64 2010). The amount of such specialized metabolites that can be extracted largely
65 depends on the density of GSTs (Paetzold *et al.*, 2010; Tissier, 2012), and so increasing
66 GST density represents a potential strategy to improve the yield of desired metabolites.
67 However, there is currently a limited understanding of the molecular mechanism of
68 GST initiation (Tissier, 2012; Huchelmann *et al.*, 2017).

69 Studies using *Arabidopsis thaliana* have provided the most detailed picture to date
70 of the transcriptional regulation of trichome initiation, and more than 30 associated
71 genes have been identified (Pattanaik *et al.*, 2014; Pesch *et al.*, 2014; Robinson &
72 Roeder, 2015; Tian *et al.*, 2017; Fambrini & Pugliesi, 2019; Schuurink & Tissier, 2019;
73 Wang *et al.*, 2021). However, *A. thaliana* trichomes are non-glandular and so this model
74 may not be a suitable reference for the initiation and development of GSTs (Serna &
75 Martin, 2006; Huchelmann *et al.*, 2017; Schuurink & Tissier, 2019). Investigations into
76 the initiation of GSTs have mainly focused on three species: tomato (*Solanum*
77 *lycopersicum*, Solanaceae), cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*, Cucurbitaceae) and *A. annua*
78 (Chalvin *et al.*, 2020). Such studies have suggested that members of the HD-ZIP IV and
79 MIXTA or MIXTA-like transcription factor (TF) families play conserved roles in GST

80 initiation in tomato and *A. annua*. In the tomato family, eight types of trichomes have
81 been identified, of which types I, IV, VI, and VII are GSTs (Glas *et al.*, 2012). Molecular
82 studies have focused on types I and VI. It has been shown that a complex formed by a
83 HD-ZIP IV protein, Woolly, and a C2H2 zinc-finger protein, Hair, play a major role in
84 the development of type I GSTs and a lesser role in type VI GSTs (Yang *et al.*, 2011;
85 Chang *et al.*, 2018). In addition, it was reported that the cyclinB2 gene, *SlCycB2*, which
86 is regulated by Woolly, is involved in the initiation of type I GSTs (Yang *et al.*, 2011).
87 *SlMixta*, which encodes a MIXTA-like protein, positively regulates type I GSTs
88 (Lashbrooke *et al.*, 2015; Ewas *et al.*, 2016), and another HD-ZIP IV TF, *SlCD2*,
89 regulates both type VI GST initiation and cuticle formation (Kimbara *et al.*, 2013).
90 Recently, a R2R3 MYB TF from tomato, *SlMYB31*, was reported to interact with
91 Woolly via a START-SAD domain (Xiong *et al.*, 2020). Studies of cucumber revealed
92 that the *csgl3* mutant has a glabrous fruit phenotype as a result of a mutation in the
93 *CsGL3* gene, which also belongs to the HD-ZIP IV subfamily (Pan *et al.*, 2015).
94 Moreover, *CsMYB6*, which encodes a MIXTA-like TF, is involved in the formation of
95 cucumber trichomes and fruit spines and is also downregulated in *csgl3* (Yang *et al.*,
96 2018).

97 In *A. annua*, two types of trichomes are present on the surface of leaves: GSTs, in
98 which artemisinin is synthesized and stored, and T-shaped trichomes (TSTs) (Duke &
99 Paul, 1993; Ferreira & Janick, 1995; Van Noorden, 2010). Due to the considerable
100 pharmaceutical value of artemisinin, there is great interest in understanding the
101 regulatory pathways that control *A. annua* GST density. Overexpression of the MYB
102 TF *AaMYB1* in *A. annua* results in an increase in GST density (Matías-Hernández *et*
103 *al.*, 2017), while other studies showed that two HD-ZIP IV TFs, *AaHD8* and *AaHD1*,
104 the respective homologs of *SlCD2* and Woolly, enhance GST initiation in *A. annua*
105 (Yan *et al.*, 2017, 2018). *AaHD8* acts upstream of *AaHD1* and forms a complex by
106 interacting with a MIXTA TF, *AaMIXTA1* (Shi *et al.*, 2018; Yan *et al.*, 2018). A GST-
107 specific TF, *AaGSW2*, was also observed to be regulated by *AaHD1* and *AaHD8*, and
108 ectopic expression of *AaGSW2*-homologs from two mint cultivars in *A. annua* induced

109 GST formation (Xie *et al.*, 2020). Such analyses have shown that several complexes
110 involving an HD-ZIP IV protein participate in GST initiation in tomato and *A. annua*.

111 We hypothesized that regulatory complexes involving an HD-ZIP IV TF, together
112 with members of other TF family proteins, such as MIXTA or MIXTA-like, trigger
113 GST initiation in *A. annua* and other GST-bearing plants. In this study, we identified a
114 MIXTA TF (AaMYB16) and a MIXTA-like TF (AaMYB5) that interacted with the
115 same domain, AaHD1. AaMYB5 was found to suppress GST initiation in *A. annua*,
116 while AaMYB16 had the opposite effect. Moreover, they showed opposite effects on
117 the DNA binding ability of AaHD1. We also determined that a JASMONATE-ZIM
118 DOMAIN (JAZ) protein can directly enhance the inhibitory effect of AaMYB5. We
119 present a mechanism for GST initiation in *A. annua* that involves TF complexes and
120 modulation by the phytohormone jasmonic acid (JA).

121

122 Materials and Methods

123 Plant materials and methyl jasmonate treatment

124 We used the *A. annua* cultivar ‘Huhao 1’ (obtained from the School of Life
125 Sciences, Southwest University, Chongqing) due to its high artemisinin content. Plants
126 were cultivated as previously described (Shen *et al.*, 2016a). Two-week-old *A. annua*
127 plants growing in a greenhouse were sprayed with 100 μ M MeJA (methyl jasmonate,
128 Sigma-Aldrich, USA) which dissolved in 0.1% ethanol or 0.1% ethanol as a mock
129 control treatment. Leaf samples were collected 0, 0.5, 1.5, 3, 6, 9, 12 and 24 hours after
130 treatment.

131 Tobacco (*Nicotiana benthamiana*) seeds were sown directly in pots and plants
132 were grown at $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ under a cycle of 16 h light and 8 h darkness for one month.

133

134 Yeast one-hybrid (Y1H) and yeast two-hybrid (Y2H) assays

135

136 Y1H experiments were conducted using the Matchmaker Gold Yeast One-Hybrid
137 System (Clontech). The open reading frames (ORFs) of *AaMYB5*, *AaMYB16* and
138 *AaHDI* were amplified by PCR using the KOD -Plus- DNA polymerase (Toyobo,
139 Osaka, Japan) which take the cDNA from young leaves as templates and ligated into
140 the pB42AD vector using ClonExpress II (Vazyme, Nanjing, China). The L1-box
141 sequence (3' X CGCAATAAATGTATCATT) and MBS-box sequence (3' X
142 AAATACTAACGGTTCGTTA) from the *AaGSW2* promoter were inserted into the
143 pLacZ vector. pB42AD-AaMYB16 or pB42AD-AaMYB5 with pLacZ-3X MBS-
144 *AaGSW2*, and pB42AD-AaHDI with pLacZ-3X L1-*AaGSW2* were co-transformed into
145 the yeast strain EGY48a. An empty pB42AD vector was used as a negative control. The
146 transformed yeast cells were grown on SD/-Trp/-Ura plates for three days. SD/-Trp/-
147 Ura plates with X-gal were used as test media. All primers used are listed in Table S1.

148 Y2H assays were performed with the Matchmaker Gold Yeast Two-Hybrid System,
149 according to the manufacturer's instructions (Takara, Japan). The full length *AaJAZ8*
150 ORF and full length or truncated *AaHDI* ORFs were amplified and ligated into the
151 pGADT7 vector. The full length *AaMYB16* ORF and full length or truncated *AaMYB5*
152 ORFs were amplified and ligated into the pGBKT7 vector. Combinations of pGADT7-
153 X and pGBKT7-X vectors were co-transformed into the yeast strain AH109. Empty
154 pGADT7 and pGBKT7 vectors were used as negative controls. The transformed yeast
155 cells were grown on DDO (SD/-Leu/-Trp) plates at 30°C for three days. Then positive
156 clones were transferred to TDO (SD/-Leu/-His/-Trp) and then QDO (SD/-Ade/-Leu/-
157 His/-Trp) medium. Yeast growth status was observed and photographed after
158 cultivation for three days at 30°C on QDO media. We added 15 mM 3-amino-1,2,4-
159 triazole into the medium to inhibit self-activation of pGBKT7-AaMYB16 and
160 pGBKT7-AaMYB5. All primers used are listed in Table S1.

161

162 Bimolecular fluorescence complementation (BiFC) assays

163 BiFC assays were carried out as previously described (Shen *et al.*, 2016a). The
164 AaHD1 ORF was amplified and inserted into the pEarleyGate201-YN vector (Earley
165 *et al.*, 2006). The AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 ORFs were amplified and individually
166 inserted into the pEarleyGate202-YC vector (Earley *et al.*, 2006). All primers used are
167 listed in Table S1. The resulting vectors were then transformed into *Agrobacterium*
168 *tumefaciens* GV3101 strain. Cultures of the *A. tumefaciens* strain containing the YN
169 vector and the strains containing either of the two YC vectors were used in injections
170 into 4-week-old *N. benthamiana* leaves. After incubation in darkness for 24 hours and
171 then light for 24 hours, images were captured using the LAS AF Lite software and a
172 laser scanning confocal microscope (Leica, Wetzlar, Germany).

173

174 Co-immunoprecipitation (Co-IP) assays

175 Co-IP assays were performed as previously described (Ma *et al.*, 2018). The
176 *AaHD1* ORF sequence without the stop codon was amplified and ligated into the pHB-
177 YFP (yellow fluorescent protein) vector (Earley *et al.*, 2006) to generate HD1-YFP
178 fusion proteins. Similarly, the *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* ORFs were separately amplified
179 and ligated into the pHB-3X flag vector (Earley *et al.*, 2006) to express the MYB5-flag
180 and MYB16-flag fusion proteins, respectively. Co-transformation of individual
181 35S::AaMYB16/AaMYB5-3X flag and PHB- X -YFP were used as controls. All
182 vectors were transformed into *A. tumefaciens* strain GV3101. pHB-AaMYB16-3X flag
183 or pHB-AaMYB16-3X flag and pHB-AaHD1-YFP were injected into 4-week-old *N.*
184 *benthamiana* leaves as previously described (Ma *et al.*, 2018). After incubation in
185 darkness for 24 hours and then light for 24 hours, leaves were ground to a powder in
186 liquid nitrogen. Proteins were extracted using lysis buffer (50 mM Tris HCl [pH 7.4],
187 150 mM NaCl, 10% glycerol, 1 mM EDTA, and 0.5% Nonidet P-40), 1 mL powdered
188 material dissolved in 1 mL buffer containing 20 μ l and protease inhibitor cocktail
189 (MedChemExpress, China) and 10 μ l MG132 (MedChemExpress, China). After
190 incubation on ice for 15 min, samples were centrifuged (1,300 g) twice for 10 min (Ma

191 *et al.*, 2018), the supernatant was transferred and mixed with the indicated 15 µl YFP
192 antibody (GeneScript, Nanjing, China) and 15 µl Protein G Sepharose (GE Healthcare,
193 Amersham, UK) for 3 h at 4°C. The immunoprecipitants were collected by magnetic
194 rack (Genscript, China) and washed at least three times with lysis buffer. These protein
195 samples were dissolved with 2X loading buffer. After boiling for 10 min and
196 centrifugation as above, the samples were fractionated on a sodium dodecyl sulfate
197 polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) then transferred onto nitrocellulose
198 membranes (Millipore). The membranes were blocked with 5 mL 3% BSA containing
199 an anti-Flag antibody (1:2000, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) and incubated with the indicated
200 primary antibodies at 4°C overnight.

201

202 Dual-luciferase transient expression assays

203 Dual-luciferase (Dual-LUC) assays were performed as previously described
204 (Edgett *et al.*, 2008). The full length or truncated *AaHDI*, *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* ORF
205 sequences were individually amplified and ligated into the pHB-YFP and pHB-Flag
206 vectors (effectors). A 1,174-bp *AaGSW2* promoter fragment was amplified and ligated
207 into the pGREEN II0800 vector to generate the reporter. The gene of the reporter
208 protein Renilla LUC (REN) was used as an internal reference and its expression was
209 driven by the constitutive 35S promoter. The empty pHB vector was used as a negative
210 control for the effectors. All vectors were transformed into *A. tumefaciens* GV3101
211 strain together with the helper plasmid pSoup 19. Various combinations of the effector
212 and reporters were mixed in a 3:2 volume ratio and injected into 4-week-old tobacco
213 leaves for transient expression. The plants were grown in darkness for 24 h and then in
214 darkness for 24 h, after which time leaf samples were collected and LUC and REN
215 activities were treated using commercial Dual-LUC reaction reagents (Dual-
216 Luciferase® Reporter Assay System, Promega E1910) and measured by GloMax 20/20
217 Luminometer (Promega, USA). All analyses were performed with three biological
218 repeats. All primers used are listed in Table S1.

219

220 *A. annua* transformation

221 The *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* ORFs were individually amplified by PCR using the
222 KOD -Plus- DNA polymerase (Toyobo, Osaka, Japan) and cloned into the pHB vector
223 for overexpression. The 352-bp fragments of *AaMYB5* and 381-bp fragments of
224 *AaMYB16* were individually recombined into the pHELLSGATE12 vector using the
225 gateway LR recombination reaction (Invitrogen) to generate RNAi vectors. We
226 individually amplified 1,855- and 1,758-bp *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* promoter regions
227 by PCR from an *A. annua* genomic DNA library, and cloned them into the pCAMBIA
228 1391Z vector (Jefferson *et al.*, 1987). All vectors were transferred into *A. tumefaciens*
229 strain EHA105 and the transformed bacteria were used to transform *A. annua* as
230 described previously (Shen *et al.*, 2012).

231

232 Phylogenetic tree construction

233 A total of 180 MYB *A. annua* transcription factor sequences were identified from
234 RNA-seq data (SRR019547 for mature leaf trichome; SRR019254 for meristem;
235 SRR019548 for bud trichome; SRR019549 for cotyledon; SRR019546 for young leaf
236 trichome) (Graham *et al.*, 2010). The data were converted to fasta format using the SRA
237 toolkit (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/sra/?view=software>). Some reference
238 sequences used in this analysis were selected from Brockington's research (Brockington *et al.*,
239 2013). Sequence alignment were performed using ClustalX (Trinity College, Dublin,
240 Ireland). The phylogenetic tree was constructed using the Mega7 software as previously
241 described (Tamura *et al.*, 2011).

242

243 RNA extraction and quantitative real time (qRT)-PCR

244 Expression pattern analysis was performed of samples of roots, stems, shoots and
245 young and old leaves (Yan *et al.*, 2017) collected from five-month-old *A. annua* plants.

246 Buds and flowers were collected 5 and 15 d after budding, respectively, and trichomes
247 were isolated from buds as previously described (Wang *et al.*, 2009). Leaf samples
248 (Leaf 1–Leaf 5, Leaf 9, Leaf 11, Leaf 16) were collected as previously described (Yan
249 *et al.*, 2017). Single tissue samples were collected from each of five independent wild
250 type *A. annua* plants. Transgenic plant samples were collected by taking the first leaf
251 below the meristem (Leaf 1) from two-month-old wild type, *AaMYB5*- and *AaMYB16*-
252 overexpressing, and RNAi transgenic plants. RNA samples were extracted using a plant
253 RNA isolation reagent (Tiangen Biotech, Beijing, China), and aliquots of 0.5 µg of total
254 RNA were used in reverse transcriptase reactions with the PrimeScript™ RT Master
255 Mix (Takara, Shiga, Japan). qRT-PCR was performed on a Roche LightCycler 96 Real-
256 Time PCR machine (Roche, Basel, Switzerland) as previously described (Shen *et al.*,
257 2016b). The $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method was used for analysis (Livak & Schmittgen, 2001). Data
258 were generated from three biological replicates. All primers used are listed in Table S1.

259

260 β -glucuronidase (GUS) staining and subcellular localization

261 Histochemical staining for GUS activity in four-week-old 1391Z-pro*AaMYB5*-
262 GUS- and 1391Z-pro*AaMYB16*-GUS-transgenic plants was performed as previously
263 described (Jefferson *et al.*, 1988). The *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* ORFs were amplified
264 without stop codons and inserted individually into the pHB-YFP vector. The *A.*
265 *tumefaciens* GV3101 strain harboring pHB-*AaMYB5*, *AaMYB16*-YFP or pHB-YFP
266 were infiltrated into four-week-old tobacco leaves. After a 24-h incubation period in
267 darkness followed by a 24-h incubation period in light, YFP signals were visualized by
268 confocal laser microscopy (Leica TCS SP5-II, Germany). All primers used are listed in
269 Table S1.

270

271 GST density and scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

272 Healthy leaves (Leaf 9) with no signs of physical damage were collected from

273 three-month-old *A. annua* plants grown in a greenhouse as previously described (Yan
274 *et al.*, 2017). Images were captured by fluorescence microscopy (Olympus, Tokyo,
275 Japan) under 5X magnification and excitation at 450–480 nm. The ImageJ software
276 (<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij>) was used to measure the leaf area and count the number of
277 GSTs, as previously described (Cheng *et al.*, 2014). Values for GST density were
278 obtained by dividing the number of GSTs by the leaf area. The experiment was
279 performed with triplicate samples.

280 Plant samples (Leaf 9) were collected as described above and then washed with
281 water, fixed, washed again, dehydrated, dried, and sputter-coated prior to SEM analysis
282 as previously described (Singh *et al.*, 2015). Images were captured with a Hitachi S-
283 4700 scanning electron microscope (Hitachi, Japan) using a 2 kV accelerating voltage.

284

285 Artemisinin content

286 Leaf samples were collected from five-month-old transgenic and wild type *A.*
287 *annua* plants, dried overnight at 50°C in an oven and then ground to a powder. The
288 powdered samples (0.1g) were extracted twice with 2 ml methanol in an ultrasonic
289 processor (JYD-650; Shanghai Zhisun Instrument Co. Ltd, Shanghai, China) at 25°C
290 and 50 W for 30 min. The samples were then centrifuged at 12,000 g for ten minutes
291 and the supernatant was passed through a 0.22- μ m nitrocellulose filter. The artemisinin
292 content was measured by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) as
293 previously described (Shen *et al.*, 2016b). The experiments included three biological
294 replicates.

295

296 Electrophoretic mobility shift assays (EMSA)

297 *AaHD1*, *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* ORF fragments were amplified and ligated into
298 the PET-30a prokaryotic expression vector for protein expression. The L1-box and
299 MBS motif probes from the *AaGSW2* promoter were synthesized and labelled with

300 biotin at their N termini by Sangon (Shanghai, China). To achieve protein expression
301 and purification, the PET30a-AaHD1, PET30a-AaMYB5/AaMYB16 and empty PET-
302 30a vector were transformed into the Rosetta (DE3) *Escherichia coli* strain (TransGen
303 Biotech, China), and expression of the recombinant proteins was induced in *E. coli*
304 cultures by adding isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside (IPTG) to a final
305 concentration of 0.5 mM at 16°C for 16 h. The proteins were purified using HisSep Ni-
306 NTA (nitrilotriacetic) Agarose Resin (Yeasen, China) according to the manufacturer's
307 instructions.

308 EMSA reactions were carried out following the instructions of the LightShift
309 Chemiluminescent EMSA Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Proteins present in
310 cultures of *E. coli* harboring the empty PET-30a vector were used as a negative control.

311

312 Yeast three-hybrid (Y3H)

313 Y3H assays were performed following the protocol of the Matchmaker GAL4
314 three-hybrid system (Takara, Japan). The *AaMYB16* ORF was amplified and ligated
315 into the pBridge vector (Takara, Japan) to create DNA binding domain fusion proteins.
316 The *AaMYB5* ORF was amplified and ligated into the pBridge-AaMYB16 vector with
317 expression driven by the MET25 promoter as a methionine (met) repressor. The *AaHD1*
318 ORF was amplified and ligated into the pGADT7 vector. pBridge-AaMYB16 or
319 pBridge-AaMYB16-AaMYB5, together with pGADT7-AaHD1, were co-transformed
320 into the yeast AH109 strain. The empty pGADT7 and pBridge vectors were used as
321 negative controls. Yeast cells containing the recombinant vectors were incubated in
322 SD/-Leu/-Trp-Met medium at 30°C for three days and then cultured in liquid SD/-Leu/-
323 Trp-Met media until the cultures reached $OD_{600} = 0.6$, then diluted by liquid media to
324 different concentrations. The cells were then plated onto solid SD/-Leu/-His/-Trp-Met
325 and SD/-Ade/-Leu/-His/-Trp-Met media. After incubation at 30°C for three days, yeast
326 cell growth was observed. β -galactosidase (β -Gal) assays were carried out following
327 the manufacturer's instructions (Takara, Japan) using chlorophenol red β -D-

328 galactopyranoside (Roche, Switzerland) as the substrate. All primers used are listed in
329 Table S1.

330

331 Results

332 **AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 competitively interact with AaHD1, a positive regulator** 333 **of GST initiation**

334 AaHD1 is known to promote GST initiation in *A. annua* by directly activating its
335 target gene, *AaGSW2* (Xie *et al.*, 2020). To identify putative AaHD1-interacting
336 proteins, we screened a complementary DNA (cDNA) library derived from young
337 leaves of *A. annua*. Several TFs were identified, two of which (Aannua03343S376100
338 and Aannua05546S508500) were found to belong to the MYB TF superfamily. The
339 presence of signature domain ‘NLSHMAQWESARLEAEAR’ indicated
340 Aannua03343S376100 belonged to SBG9-A (subgroup9 of R2R3MYB factors)
341 subclade which includes MIXTA and MIXTA-like TFs (Brockington *et al.*, 2013).
342 The presence of signature domain ‘SPSTRMAQWESARLEAEARLS’ indicated
343 Aannua05546S508500 belonged to SBG9-B subclade which includes MYB17 and
344 MYB17-like TFs. A phylogenetic analysis in *A. annua* indicated that
345 Aannua03343S376100 is closely related to the AaMIXTA1, which promoted GST
346 initiation in *A. annua* (Shi *et al.*, 2018) while Aannua05546S508500 was not clustered
347 with AaMIXTA1 (Fig. S1a). A phylogenetic analysis with TFs that are known to be
348 related to SBG9 TFs (Brockington *et al.*, 2013) showed that Aannua03343S376100 and
349 its closest relatives were clustered with MIXTA-like subclade including AtMYB16
350 which positively regulated epidermal conical cells in *Arabidopsis* (Oshima *et al.*,
351 2013). Aannua05546S508500 and its closest relatives were clustered with AtMYB17
352 belonged to MYB17 subclade (Fig. S1b) (Zhang *et al.*, 2009). We named
353 Aannua03343S376100 and Aannua05546S508500 as AaMYB16 and AaMYB5,
354 respectively.

355 We next used Y2H, BiFC and Co-IP assays to confirm the interaction between
356 AaHD1 and AaMYB16/MYB5 *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Fig.1 a, b, c, d and S2). AaHD1 has

357 the four domains that are typical of members of the HD-Zip IV subfamily (Fig. 1e) :
358 the HD and LZ domains are responsible for their specific promoter-binding activity,
359 while the START and SAD domains mediate protein interactions (Ariel *et al.*, 2007).
360 To identify the domain in AaHD1 that is responsible for interactions with AaMYB16
361 and AaMYB5, we performed Y2H assays with truncated domain variants of the AaHD1
362 protein. These revealed that AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 interact with the same START-
363 SAD domains. Furthermore, an HD-LZ domain or a single START and SAD domain
364 were not sufficient for binding to occur between AaHD1 and AaMYB5 or AaMYB16.
365 However, binding did occur when both the START and SAD domains were present,
366 potentially as a complex (Fig. 1f). Given that AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 interacted with
367 AaHD1 via the same domain, we hypothesized that they compete with each other for
368 AaHD1 binding sites. To test this, we used Y3H assays and observed that AaMYB5
369 significantly suppressed the growth of AaHD1- and AaMYB16-expressing yeast cells
370 (Fig. 1g), which is consistent with AaMYB5 attenuating the interaction between
371 AaMYB16 and AaHD1 (Fig. 1h). β -Gal activity assays confirmed this result (Fig. 1i).
372 Taken together, these results indicate that AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 competitively bind
373 to the START–SAD domain of AaHD1.

374 **AaMYB16 expression is GST- and TST-specific while AaMYB5 is specific to GSTs** 375 **only**

376 We investigated the expression of *AaMYB16* and *AaMYB5* in different organs and
377 tissues (root, stem, young leaf, old leaf, shoot, bud, flower and trichomes) using qRT-
378 PCR. Their expression was highest in trichomes, followed by buds, young leaves and
379 flowers, while expression levels were extremely low in stems and roots (Fig. 2a, b). We
380 also observed decreasing expression of both genes as leaves aged (Fig. 2c, d). Notably,
381 the expression patterns of both the genes correlated with the formation of GSTs. To
382 further resolve the expression data, we constructed two vectors, *1391-proAaMYB16*
383 containing the putative *AaMYB16* promoter region and *1391-proAaMYB5-GUS*
384 containing the putative *AaMYB5* promoter region, and fused each to a GUS reporter
385 gene. We then separately transformed the vectors into wild type *A. annua* plants.

386 Through histochemical staining of two-week-old transgenic plants containing *1391-*
387 *proAaMYB16* or *1391-pro AaMYB5-GUS*, GUS was only detected in very young non-
388 expanded leaves (Fig. S3). Strong staining was apparent in only the GSTs of *1391-*
389 *proAaMYB5-GUS* transgenic plants, while staining was observed in TSTs and GSTs of
390 *1391-proAaMYB16-GUS* transgenic plants (Fig. 2e).

391 We investigated the subcellular localization of both AaMYB6 and MYB5 by
392 transiently expressing each as fusion protein in *N. benthamiana* leaves. Both were
393 localized to the nucleus, while free YFP was distributed throughout the cell (Fig. 2f),
394 which is consistent with their putative roles as TFs. These results suggested that
395 AaMYB16 is a trichome-specific transcription factor, while AaMYB5 is a glandular
396 trichome-specific transcription factor, and that both may be involved in the regulation
397 of trichome formation in *A. annua*.

398

399 **AaMYB16 promotes both GST and TST initiation, while AaMYB5 inhibits GST** 400 **formation**

401 To further test the hypothesis that AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 regulate trichome
402 development, we generated transgenic *A. annua* lines that constitutively over-expressed
403 AaMYB16 or AaMYB5 (35S::*AaMYB16* and 35S::*AaMYB5*, respectively), as well as
404 transgenic lines in which expression of each gene was individually silenced by RNAi.
405 After verification of the presence of the appropriate transgene and relative expression
406 analysis of *AaMYB16* and *AaMYB17* by PCR, three *AaMYB16* overexpression lines
407 from 13 lines, three *AaMYB16* knockdown lines from 6 lines, three *AaMYB17*
408 overexpression lines from 7 lines, and four *AaMYB17* knockdown lines from 13 lines
409 were randomly selected for phenotype analysis (Fig. 3a-d). Compared with the wild
410 type plants, GST density on the adaxial side of mature leaves (Leaf 9) was 28–45%
411 higher in *AaMYB16*-overexpression transgenic lines and 27–41% lower in *AaMYB16*-
412 knock down lines (Fig. 3e, g). SEM analysis showed that the non-glandular trichome
413 density was also higher in overexpression lines and lower in the RNAi lines (Fig. S4).

414 We also measured artemisinin levels and found them to be 43–56% higher in the
415 overexpression lines and 19–27% lower in the RNAi lines, which correlated with GST
416 density data (Fig. 3i). These results suggest that AaMYB16 acts as a positive regulator
417 of both GST and TST formation.

418 AaMYB5 had the opposite effect to that of AaMYB16 in that GST density was
419 46–69% higher in the *AaMYB5*-knockdown lines and 28–39% lower in the *AaMYB5*-
420 overexpressing lines (Fig. 3f, h). SEM analysis indicated no difference in TST density
421 between the wild type and transgenic plants (Fig. S4). Artemisinin levels were 45–84%
422 higher in the *AaMYB5*-knockdown lines and 15–27% lower in *AaMYB5*-overexpressing
423 lines (Fig. 3j). Meanwhile, the growth condition of wild-type and transgenic plants
424 showed no significant difference (Fig. S5). Collectively these results suggest that
425 AaMYB5 is a negative regulator of GST formation.

426

427 **AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 antagonistically affect the transcriptional activation of** 428 ***AaHD1***

429 Recently, we identified a GST-specific WRKY TF, AaGSW2, from *A. annua* that
430 is regulated by AaHD1 and found that it plays a central role in GST initiation (Xie *et*
431 *al.*, 2020). Here, we examined *AaGSW2* expression in the *AaMYB16*- and *AaMYB5*-
432 transgenic plants (Fig. 4a, b) and found that *AaMYB16* expression correlated with
433 *AaGSW2* expression, while the expression of *AaMYB5* showed an inverse correlation
434 with *AaGSW2* expression (Fig. 4a, b). However, in Y1H and Dual-LUC assays, we
435 found that neither AaMYB16 nor AaMYB5 bound to, or activated, the *AaGSW2*
436 promoter of (Fig. 4c, e). Given our observations that both AaMYB16 and AaMYB5
437 interacted with AaHD1, we hypothesized that the two MYB TFs indirectly regulate
438 *AaGSW2* expression by affecting the function of AaHD1. To test this, we carried out
439 Dual-LUC assays to evaluate *AaGSW2* promoter activity using combinations of AaHD1
440 with AaMYB5 or AaMYB16. We observed that AaMYB16 greatly strengthened the
441 activation by AaHD1 of the *AaGSW2* promoter, while AaMYB5 significantly weakened

442 the activation (Fig. 4d, e). Given that AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 competitively interact
443 with AaHD1, we investigated whether AaMYB5 could reduce the AaMYB16 enhanced
444 AaHD1 transcriptional activity using Dual-LUC assays. While ensuring that the
445 concentration of effectors (AaMYB16 and AaHD1) and reporter AaGSW2 remained
446 constant, we found that promoter activity of *AaGSW2* declined with an increasing
447 concentration of AaMYB5 (Fig. 4f). These results indicate that AaMYB16 and
448 AaMYB5 have opposite effects on the transcriptional activity of *AaHD1*.

449

450 **AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 function in GST initiation is largely dependent on** 451 **AaHD1**

452 To further investigate the regulatory effects of AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 on the
453 transcriptional activity of *AaHD1*, we performed EMSA, using the *AaGSW2*
454 promoter L1 box as a probe. The intensity of the shifted band significantly increased
455 with the addition of 2 µg His-AaMYB16. When 2 µg, 4 µg, 6 µg and 8 µg of His-
456 AaMYB5 were added in turn, the band intensity sequentially decreased (Fig. 4g, h).
457 This indicated that the DNA binding ability of AaHD1 was enhanced by AaMYB16
458 but attenuated by AaMYB5.

459 We then investigated whether the effects of AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 on
460 AaHD1 relied on physical interactions between the proteins. To this end, we disrupted
461 the interaction between AaHD1 and AaMYB5/MYB16 by making a H474D mutation
462 in the START domain and a H598D mutation in the SAD domain of AaHD1 (AaHD1-
463 mST) (Zhang *et al.*, 2010) to prevent interaction between AaHD1 and
464 AaMYB16/AaMYB5 while not influencing the DNA-binding activity of AaHD1 (Fig.
465 S5a, c). Dual-LUC assays showed that the activation of the *AaGSW2* promoter by
466 AaHD1 alone was not affected by the AaHD1-mST mutation (Fig. 4i, k). However,
467 the combined effect of AaHD1 and AaMYB5 or AaMYB16 on promoter activation
468 was blocked by the AaHD1-mST mutation (Fig. 4i, k). This indicated that the
469 stimulatory or suppressive effects of AaMYB16 or AaMYB5 on transcriptional

470 activation of *AaGSW2*, respectively, by AaHD1 was dependent on interactions
471 between the MYB TFs and AaHD1.

472 We next generated a form of AaHD1 in which the HD and LZ domains had been
473 removed (termed C-AaHD1) to abolish DNA binding activity. The R2R3 domains of
474 AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 were also deleted (termed C-AaMYB5 and C-AaMYB16,
475 respectively) in order to eliminate DNA binding activity but not affect their protein-
476 protein interaction characteristics (Zhang *et al.*, 2010) (Fig. 1f, S7c). Dual-LUC assays
477 showed that the domain deletions in C-AaHD1 altered the stimulatory or suppressive
478 effects of AaHD1 combined with AaMYB16 or AaMYB5, although protein
479 interactions still occurred (Fig. 4j, l). However, C-AaMYB5 and C-AaMYB16 had no
480 affect when each was combined with AaHD1 (Fig. 4j, l). These data indicated that
481 AaHD1 plays a principal role in the AaHD1-AaMYB5/AaMYB16 complex and that
482 the function of the complex is greatly dependent on the DNA-binding activity of
483 AaHD1 but not on that of AaMYB5 and AaMYB16.

484 Based on these results, we hypothesized that the regulatory functions of AaMYB5
485 and AaMYB16 on GST formation were predominantly associated with AaHD1 action.
486 To test this, we overexpressed *AaMYB5* or *AaMYB16* in an *AaHD1*-silenced line
487 (RNAi-*AaHD1*-19) and of the resulting transgenic lines, six were chosen for further
488 analysis: RNAi-HD1-AaMYB5-9 (LMYB5-9), RNAi-HD1-AaMYB5-11 (LMYB5-
489 11), RNAi-HD1-AaMYB5-14 (LMYB5-14), RNAi-HD1-AaMYB16-38 (LMYB16-
490 38), RNAi-HD1-AaMYB16-53 (LMYB16-53) and RNAi-HD1-AaMYB16-57
491 (LMYB16-57) (Figure 5b, c). Line RNAi-*AaHD1*-19 was used as a control. We found
492 that the negative effect of AaMYB5 and positive effect of AaMYB16 on GST
493 formation was greatly reduced in the RNAi-*AaHD1*-19 background, as indicated by
494 the comparable *AaGSW2* expression levels, GST densities and the artemisinin contents
495 of all six lines to those of RNAi-*AaHD1*-19 (Fig. 5a-e). These results indicated that
496 the regulatory effects of AaMYB5 and AaMYB16 on GST formation were largely
497 dependent on the presence of AaHD1.

498

499 **JA regulates AaMYB5 but not AaMYB16**

500 The expression of *AaHD1* is regulated by JA via interaction with AaJA8, a
501 repressor of the JA signaling pathway (Yan *et al.*, 2017). To investigate whether JA also
502 regulates *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16*, we performed qRT-PCR and found that a JA
503 treatment of *A. annua* plants significantly down-regulated the expression of *AaMYB5*
504 but did not affect the expression of *AaMYB16* (Fig. 6a, b). Moreover, Y2H and BiFC
505 analyses revealed that AaMYB5, but not AaMYB16, interacted with AaJAZ8 (Fig. 6c,
506 d). Given that JAZ proteins are typically reported to be inhibitors of the proteins with
507 which they interact (Chini *et al.*, 2007), based on our results the predicted action of
508 AaJAZ8 would be to suppress the inhibitory activity of AaMYB5 on GST formation,
509 and JA application would accordingly reduce GST formation. However, JA has been
510 reported to promote the initiation of GSTs (Maes *et al.*, 2011). To address this apparent
511 contradiction, we performed Dual-LUC assays and found that AaJAZ8 significantly
512 enhanced rather than inhibited the repression activity of AaMYB5 on the transcriptional
513 activation of AaHD1 (Fig. 6e). Further, in a Y2H assay AaJAZ8 interacted with the
514 AaMYB5 N-terminus (Fig. 6f, g). Dual-LUC analysis also indicated that the promotion
515 of AaMYB5 repression of the transcriptional activation of AaHD1 by AaJAZ8 depends
516 on its interaction with AaMYB5 (Fig. 6h). Thus, AaJAZ8 functions as a co-inhibitory
517 partner, acting with AaMYB5 to regulate GST formation.

518

519 **Discussion**

520 In this current study, we identified two complexes that include HD-ZIP IV AaHD1: one
521 with the MIXTA TF AaMYB16, and one with the MIXTA-like TF AaMYB5.
522 AaMYB16 promotes GST initiation, while AaMYB5 has the opposite effect, and they
523 also have antagonistic effects on the DNA-binding ability of AaHD1. Notably, neither
524 AaMYB16 nor AaMYB5 independently regulate GST initiation without AaHD1, which
525 indicates that the HD-ZIP IV TF plays a central role in the HD-ZIP IV-MIXTA complex.
526 Our previous study identified an AaHD8-AaMIXTA1 complex that affects cuticle
527 development by directly binding to cuticle synthesis genes and regulates GST initiation

528 by directly binding to the target gene *AaHDI* (Yan *et al.*, 2018). Dual-LUC assays also
529 showed that the function of AaMIXTA1 is largely dependent on AaHD8 action (Fig.
530 S8), which is consistent with the roles of AaMYB16 and AaMYB5. These results
531 suggest conserved epidermis-related functions of HD-ZIP IV and MIXTA or MIXTA-
532 like TFs in *A. annua*. Similar epidermis-related functions of HD-ZIP IV and MIXTA-
533 like are also apparent in other plant species. For example, in cotton (*Gossypium*
534 *hirsutum*) the HD-ZIP IV TF GhHD1 (GbML1) and MIXTA-like TF GhMYB25
535 (GbMYB25) promote fiber elongation and have been shown to interact with each other
536 via the START-SAD domain of the HD-ZIP IV partner (Machado *et al.*, 2009; Zhang
537 *et al.*, 2010; Walford *et al.*, 2012).

538 TFs from the HD-ZIP IV and MIXTA or MIXTA-like subfamilies are also
539 involved in GST initiation in other plant species: two genes from tobacco (*Nicotiana*
540 *tabacum*), *NtHD-ZIP-IV-1* and *NtHD-ZIP-IV-2*, which are homologs of *WOOLLY*, are
541 specifically expressed in leaves and shoots that are covered by GSTs (Zhang *et al.*,
542 2019); a homolog of *CsGL3 GLABROUS* from melon (*Cucumis melo*), CmGL, encodes
543 a HD-ZIP TF that has been reported to regulate multicellular trichome initiation (Zhu
544 *et al.*, 2017); and *AmMIXTA* and *AmMYBML1* from snapdragon (*Antirrhinum majus*)
545 regulate epidermal conical-cell shape and trichome formation (Noda *et al.*, 1994; Perez-
546 Rodriguez *et al.*, 2005). Cotton GhMML3 (Wan *et al.*, 2016), GhMML4 (Wu *et al.*,
547 2018), GhMML7 (Machado *et al.*, 2009), GhMML8 (Tian & Zhang, 2021), GhMML9
548 (Tian & Zhang, 2021) and GhMML10 (Tian & Zhang, 2021) also play important roles
549 in fiber formation. Other MIXTA/MIXTA-like TFs related to GST initiation or
550 epidermal cell formation have been identified, including the MIXTA-like gene
551 *PhMYB1* from *Petunia hybrida*, which affects epidermal cell shape (Baumann *et al.*,
552 2007). Additionally, *MtMYBML3* from *Medicago truncatula* is highly expressed in
553 young vegetative buds that contain developing GSTs (Gilding & Marks, 2010) and
554 *MgMYBML8* from *Mimulus guttatus* negatively regulates leaf GST density (Scoville *et*
555 *al.*, 2011). Taken together with our results, these reports indicate that the HD-ZIP IV-
556 MIXTA complex plays significant roles in GST initiation.

557 Based on our analyses, we propose a model of JA-regulated GST initiation in *A.*
558 *annua* (Fig. 7). In the absence of JA, the proteins JAZ8, AaMYB5 and AaHD1 interact
559 with each other to form an inhibitory complex in which AaHD1 loses its ability to bind
560 to the *AaGSW2* promoter (Fig. 7). Thus, AaHD1 cannot activate the expression of
561 *AaGSW2* and epidermal cells do not differentiate into GSTs. Conversely, in the presence
562 of JA, expression of *AaMYB5* decreases and AaJAZ8 is degraded. Consequently,
563 AaHD1 is released from the inhibitory complex and binds to the *AaGSW2* promoter.
564 AaMYB16 can interact with free AaHD1 to form an activated complex, which leads to
565 a synergistic effect on binding to the promoter of AaHD1 and enhanced GST initiation
566 by transcriptional activation of *AaGSW2*.

567

568 **Accession numbers**

569 AaMYB16 (KX465136.1); AaMYB5 (KX465138.1); AaHD1 (KU744599); AaGSW2
570 (KX465129.1).

571

572 **Author contributions:** Tang Kexuan conceived the project; Xie Lihui and Tang
573 Kexuan designed the research; Xie Lihui, Yan Tingxiang, Li Ling performed the
574 research; Xie Lihui, Chen Minghui, Qin Wei, Liu Hang, Chen Tiantian, Fu Xueqing,
575 Shen Qian and Jocelyn K.C. Rose analyzed the data. The authors declare no conflict of
576 interest.

577

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584

585 **Data and materials availability:** All data required to evaluate the conclusions in the

586 paper are present in the paper and/or the Supplementary Materials.

587

588 **Fig. 1 AaMYB16 and AaMYB5 competitively interact with AaHD1, a positive**
589 **regulator of glandular secretory trichome (GST) formation (a)**
590 AaMYB16/AaMYB5 fused with a DNA-binding domain in the pGBKT7 vector
591 (pGBKT7-AaMYB16/AaMYB5) and AaHD1 fused with an activation domain in the
592 pGADT7 vector (pGADT7-AaHD1). pGADT7 (AD)/ pGBKT7 (BD) alone was used
593 as the control. These constructs were transformed into yeast cells grown on each of
594 the three media: SD/-Trp/-Leu (DDO), SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His (TDO), or SD/-Trp/-Leu/-
595 His/-Ade (QDO). (b) Bimolecular fluorescence complementation assay in *Nicotiana*
596 *benthamiana* leaves. AaHD1 was fused to a N-terminal fragment of yellow
597 fluorescent protein (AaHD1-nYFP) and AaMYB16/AaMYB5 were fused with the C-
598 terminal fragment (AaM16/AaMYB5-cYFP). Different combinations of the
599 constructs were co-expressed in *N. benthamiana* leaves and the cells were then
600 visualized using confocal microscopy. Scale bars, 20 μ m. (c, d) Co-
601 immunoprecipitation of transiently co-expressed AaMYB16/AaMYB5-3xFlag and
602 AaHD1-YFP in *N. benthamiana* leaves. Protein extracts before (Input) and after
603 immunoprecipitation (IP), and anti-YFP antibody-conjugated beads were detected by
604 Western blot analysis with an anti-Flag antibody. (e) Schematic diagrams of the
605 AaHD1 protein containing four conserved domains. (f) Domain-deletion yeast two-
606 hybrid (Y2H) assay using samples obtained by the same method as in panel (a). (g)
607 Schematic representation of the bait and prey constructs used in Y3H assays. AaHD1
608 was fused with the activation domain (AD), and AaMYB16 was fused with the
609 binding domain (BD). AaMYB5 was induced by the *PMet25* promoter. (h) Yeast cells
610 transformed with bait and prey vectors were grown on two selective media: SD/-Trp/-
611 Leu/-Met (SD/-T/-L/-M) and SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His/-Ade/-Met (SD/-T/-L/-H/-A/-M).
612 The different dilutions (10^0 , 10^{-1} , and 10^{-2}) are shown at the top of the panel. (i) β -Gal
613 activities of yeast cells containing different construct combinations from (b) were
614 measured. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n = 3). Student's t-test: **, $P <$
615 0.01.

616

617 **Fig. 2 Characterization of AaMYB16/AaMYB5.** (a, b, c, d) Relative expression levels
618 of *AaMYB16/AaMYB5* in leaves at different positions and other tissues (roots, stems,
619 flowers, shoots, buds, young leaves, old leaves and trichomes) were measured by
620 quantitative reverse transcription PCR. *Actin* (EU531837) was used as an internal
621 reference. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n=3). (e) GUS expression in
622 immature, unfurled leaves of plants transformed with *1391-proAaMYB16-GUS* or
623 *1391-proAaMYB5-GUS*. GST, glandular trichome; TST, T-shaped trichome. Scale bars,
624 50 μ m. (f) Subcellular localization of 35S:AaMYB16/MYB5-YFP in tobacco leaf
625 epidermal cells. Yellow color indicates yellow fluorescent protein (YFP). Scale bars,
626 20 μ m.

627

628 **Fig. 3 *AaMYB16/AaMYB5* expression affect *Artemisia annua* glandular trichome**
629 **initiation.** (a-d) Gene expression levels of *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16* in transgenic *A.*
630 *annua* plants. OE: overexpression; i: RNAi; CK and CK1: wild type plants. *Actin* was
631 used as an internal reference. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n=3).
632 Student's t-test: **, $P < 0.01$. (e, f) Adaxial glandular trichomes of mature leaves
633 collected from *AaMYB16-/AaMYB5-* transgenic plants. Fluorescence microscopy
634 images showing the autofluorescence of glandular trichomes (yellow spots) and
635 chlorophyll (red background). Scale bars, 200 μ m. (g, h) Density of adaxial glandular
636 trichomes on mature leaves collected from *AaMYB16-/AaMYB5-*transgenic plants. Data
637 values correspond to the means \pm SD (n = 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$.
638 (i, j) Artemisinin content in *AaMYB16-* and *AaMYB5-*transgenic and wild type plants
639 was measured by high-performance liquid chromatography. Data are means \pm SD (n =
640 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$.

641

642 **Fig. 4 *AaMYB16* enhances while *AaMYB5* represses *AaHD1* activation of**
643 ***AaGSW2*.** (a, b) The expression levels of *AaGSW2* in *AaMYB16-* and *AaMYB5-*
644 transgenic plants. Relative expression levels were measured by qRT-PCR. *Actin* was
645 used as an internal reference. Wild-type plants were used as the control. Data values
646 correspond to the means \pm SD (n=3). *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$; Student's t-test. (c) Yeast
647 one-hybrid assays. AD, pB42AD. Empty vectors were used as negative controls. (d)
648 Schematic diagrams of the effector (pHB-*AaHD1*-YFP and pHB-*AaMYB16*-3X
649 Flag/*AaMYB5*-3X Flag) and reporter (35S: REN- proGSW2 - LUC) vectors used in
650 dual-luciferase (Dual-LUC) assays. (e, f) Transient transcriptional activity assay
651 showing the activation of the *AaGSW2* promoter by *AaMYB5* and *AaMYB16*. The
652 *AaGSW2* promoter was fused to the LUC reporter and promoter activity was
653 determined using a transient Dual-LUC assay in tobacco. Relative LUC activity was
654 normalized to the activity of the reference Renilla (REN) luciferase. (g) Probes:
655 *AaGSW2* promoter *L1*-box and *MBS*-box. (h) The concentration of the probe in each

656 lane was 50 pM. Lanes 1–6 contained L1 probes and lanes 7 and 8 contained MBS
657 probes. Lanes 1–6 contained 2 μ g His-AaHD1 proteins, lanes 2–7 contained 2 μ g His-
658 AaMYB16 proteins, and lane 8 contained 2 μ g His-AaMYB5 proteins. In lanes 3–6,
659 His-AaMYB5 proteins were added in increasing amounts of 2, 4, 6, and 8 μ g,
660 respectively. (i, k) AaHD1-mST represents an AaHD1 mutant with two amino acids
661 deleted in the START and SAD domains. An effector (pHB-AaHD1-YFP, pHB-
662 AaHD1-mST-YFP, or pHB-AaMYB16-3X Flag/AaMYB5-3 X Flag) and reporter (35S:
663 REN-proAaGSW2-LUC) were combined and then transiently expressed in tobacco
664 leaves. (j, l) C-AaMYB16/MYB5 correspond to the AaMYB16 and MYB5 proteins,
665 respectively, with a deletion of their respective R2R3 domain. C-AaHD1 corresponds
666 to the AaHD1 protein from which the HD and LZ domains have been deleted. An
667 effector (pHB-C-AaHD1-YFP and pHB-C-AaMYB16-3X Flag/C-AaMYB5-3X Flag)
668 and reporter (35S: REN-proAaGSW2-LUC) were combined and then transiently
669 expressed in tobacco leaves. The relative activities were normalized to the activity of
670 the reference Renilla (REN) luciferase. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n =
671 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$.

672

673 **Fig. 5 AaMYB16/AaMYB5 overexpression in AaHD1 RNAi plants.** Lines LMYB5-
674 9, LMYB5-11, and LMYB5-14 overexpress *AaMYB5* and lines LMYB16-53,
675 LMYB16-57, and LMYB16-38 overexpress *AaMYB16* in iAaHD1-19 plants. Wild type
676 (CK3) and iAaHD1-19 plants were used as controls. (a) Adaxial glandular trichomes
677 on mature leaves collected from CK3, iAaHD1-19, L9, and L53. Fluorescence
678 microscopy images of the autofluorescence of glandular trichomes (yellow spots) and
679 chlorophyll (red). Scale bars, 200 μ m. (b) Expression levels of AaHD1, AaMYB5, and
680 AaGSW2 in CK3, iAaHD1-19, LMYB5-9, LMYB5-11, and LMYB5-14 plants. (c)
681 Expression levels of AaHD1, AaMYB16, and AaGSW2 in CK3, iAaHD1-19,
682 LMYB16-53, LMYB16-57, and LMYB16-38 plants. *Actin* was used as an internal
683 reference. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n = 3). Student's t-test: *, $P <$
684 0.05; **, $P < 0.01$. (d) Densities of adaxial glandular trichomes on mature leaves

685 collected from CK3, iAaHD1-19, LMYB5-9, LMYB5-11, LMYB5-14, LMYB16-53,
686 LMYB16-57, and LMYB16-38 plants. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n =
687 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$. (e) Artemisinin contents of CK3, iAaHD1-
688 19, L9, L11, L14, L53, L57, and L38 plants. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD
689 (n = 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$.

690

691 **Fig. 6 *AaMYB5* is regulated by MeJA.** (a, b) Relative expression levels of *AaMYB5*
692 and *AaMYB16* in plants treated with methyl jasmonate (MeJA, 100 μ M). (c) Yeast two-
693 hybrid (Y2H) assay. *AaMYB5* fused to a DNA-binding domain in the pGBKT7 vector
694 (pGBKT7-*AaMYB5*), *AaJAZ8* fused to an activation domain in the pGADT7 vector
695 (pGADT7-*AaJAZ8*). AD/BD alone was used as the control. These constructs were
696 transformed into yeast cells grown on each of the three media: SD/-Trp/-Leu (DDO),
697 SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His (TDO), SD/-Trp/-Leu/-His/-Ade (QDO). (d) Bimolecular
698 fluorescence complementation assay in *Nicotiana benthamiana* leaves. *AaJAZ8* was
699 fused to the N-terminal fragment of the yellow fluorescent protein (*AaJAZ8*-nYFP),
700 *AaMYB5* was fused to the C-terminal fragment (*AaMYB5*-cYFP). The constructs were
701 co-expressed in *N. benthamiana* leaves and the cells were then visualized using
702 confocal microscopy. Scale bars, 20 μ m. (e) Transient Dual-LUC assay in tobacco
703 leaves. The empty vector was used as a negative control. The relative activities were
704 normalized to the activity of the reference Renilla (REN) luciferase. Each experiment
705 was performed with three biological replicates. Data values correspond to the means \pm
706 SD (n = 3). Student's t-test: *, $P < 0.05$; **, $P < 0.01$. (f) Schematic diagrams of the
707 *AaMYB5* protein containing two conserved domains. (g) Domain-deletion Y2H assay.
708 (h) Transient transcriptional activity assay showing the activation of the *AaGSW2*
709 promoter by *AaMYB5* and *AaJAZ8*. The *AaGSW2* promoter was fused to the LUC
710 reporter and promoter activity was determined by a transient dual-LUC assay in tobacco.
711 The relative activities were normalized to the activity of the reference Renilla (REN)
712 luciferase. Data values correspond to the means \pm SD (n = 3). Student's t-test: *, $P <$
713 0.05.

714

715 **Fig. 7 A regulatory model of *Artemisia annua* glandular trichome initiation by an**
716 **AaHD1-AaMYB16/AaMYB5 complex.** In the absence of jasmonate (JA), AaJAZ8,
717 AaMYB5 and AaHD1 interact with each other to form a complex that inhibits the
718 ability of AaHD1 to bind to the *AaGSW2* promoter. Consequently, AaHD1 does not
719 activate the expression of *AaGSW2* and epidermal cells do not differentiate into
720 glandular secretory trichomes (GSTs). In the presence of JA, expression of *AaMYB5*
721 decreases and AaJAZ8 is degraded, releasing AaHD1 from the inhibitory complex to
722 bind to the *AaGSW2* promoter. AaMYB16 can interact with free AaHD1 to form an
723 activator complex, leading to a synergistic effect on promoter-binding of AaHD1 to
724 induce GST initiation by activating *AaGSW2* transcription.

725

726 **Supplemental Information**

727 Fig. S1 Phylogenetic analyses of AaMYB5 and AaMYB16.

728

729 Fig. S2 Negative control of the fusion constructs co-expressed in *Nicotiana*
730 *benthamiana* leaves.

731

732 Fig. S3 Promoter-GUS (p*AaMYB5*/P*AaMYB16*-GUS) expression *Artemisia annua*
733 plants.

734

735 Fig. S4 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis on leaves of *AaMYB16* and
736 *AaMYB5* transgenic *Artemisia annua* plants.

737

738 Fig. S5 Growth condition of *AaMYB16* and *AaMYB5* transgenic *Artemisia annua* plants.

739

740 Fig. S6 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis on leaves of *AaMYB16* and
741 *AaMYB5* overexpressing *Artemisia annua* plants which in *AaHD1*-RNAi background.

742

743 Fig. S7 The binding effects of mutating or truncating AaHD1 and the negative control
744 of the fused constructs co-expressed in *N. benthamiana* leaves.

745

746 Fig. S8 The interaction between AaMIXTA1 and AaHD8 is necessary for AaMIXTA1
747 function.

748

749 Table. S1 Primers used in this study.

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